

Cinema, Geopolitics, and Power Surveillance: Screening Middle East in Post-9/11 Hollywood Films

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Abstract

This paper tries to investigate the ways in which American geopolitical hegemony operates through popular culture produced in the wake of 9/11. Specifically, it examines how American geopolitical anxieties and sensibilities are aesthetically, culturally and politically mediated and maintained via the cultural and politicized medium of film. It chooses *The Kingdom* (2007), a geographically informed and geopolitically framed film, as its primary source of analysis to interrogate the ways in which geopolitical anxieties and sensibilities manifest in the film's narrative through the use of geopoliticized rhetoric of screened landscapes and the specific narration of "Self"/"Other" identities. Drawing on literature from popular geopolitics, geocriticism, visual politics, and postmodernism, this research analyzes how the various interdependent registers of mapping intersect to geopolitically produce and imagine the Middle East. It maintains that the rhetoric discourse of "war on terrorism" is cinematically appropriated and geopolitically manipulated in order to diffuse and reproduce American global hegemony on the global stage. In so doing, it moves beyond the mere analysis of popular culture as only an object for analysis in world politics to how cinematic texts are sites wherein specific modes of geopolitical knowledge, geo-power and world politics are communicated and understood globally.

Keywords: Hollywood cinema; popular culture; "war on terrorism"; Middle East; international politics; global hegemony, critical geopolitics

1. Introduction: Cinema, Politics, and Representation

"As a technology of seeing and a form of projectionism, film can be regarded as eminently geo-graph-ical and geo-political."¹

Throughout the history of cinema, the landscape and culture of Middle East have been important to the discourse of Hollywood cinematic perceptions, reproductions and codifications of mythical, political and ideological discursive narratives. In particular, movies, as popular cultural artifacts, have played an extremely important, if frequently controversial, role in the mobilization of political culture, geography and propaganda. World nations and governments have tremendously relied on the power of the moving images to spread their soft power in the global sphere, and thus help create particular sentiments and discourses that ultimately work for the fulfillment of specific ends, nationally and internationally². Given its pervasive influence and potency as a strategic communication on the global stage, soft power is considered to be instrumental for the United States as it consistently seeks to maintain global hegemony and nation-branding. The medium of cinema, in other words, has been deployed to sustain prevailing political sensibilities by dramatizing stories of nationalism, heroism, villainy and geo-power as a narrative strategy to refashion a new sense of American power round the globe. Films like *Syriana* (Stephen Gaghan, 2005), *Munich* (Steven Spielberg, 2005), *Home of the Brave* (Irwin Winkler, 2006), *Redacted* (De Palma, 2007), *Body of Lies* (Ridley Scott, 2008), or *Zero Dark Thirty* (Kathryn Bigelow, 2012) are cases in point which exhibit these tendencies and sensibilities in more subtle ways.

Hence, given the power influence of popular culture in producing and authorizing knowledge about distant cultures, peoples and lands, cinema, as a powerful popular signifying system, is therefore able to vehicle, institute and normalize the established socio-political constructions and mythologies it consistently purports and perpetuates. As Mark Lacy has noted, "cinema

becomes a space where "common" sense ideas about global politics and history are (re)produced and where stories about what is acceptable behaviour from states and individuals are naturalized and legitimated"³. Cinema, as an art, then, is never neutral, but is always shaped by the political, social and economic sensibilities, anxieties, and forces that in turn shape and reshape representations of reality. Mao Zedong postulates that, "there is in fact no such thing as art for art's sake, art that stands above classes or art that is detached or independent of politics"⁴. What is more, "popular culture", to borrow Weldes and Rowely's words, "not only reflects but also constitutes world politics"⁵. Films, as popular cultural texts, discursively construct the world politics, the subjects and the objects they visually introduce to the audience, therefore illustrating the centrality of strategic cinema in shaping identities, geographies and perceptions of surveillance and international politics.

Keeping with the scope of this intervention, the complex connections between cinema, geopolitics, power and representation matter a great deal in contemporary Hollywood geopolitically-inclined films featuring the Middle East after the vents of 9/11. Following the attacks on the Pentagon in Washington and the World Trade center in New York, Pentagon officials conducted a series of meetings with Hollywood directors, screenwriters, scenarists and specialists in disaster movies to "solicit the help of Hollywood in the war against terrorism"⁶ and put forward possible scenarios to dramatize and respond to the attacks threatening American identity as an international hegemon. In a similar vein, White House advisors met with Hollywood executives to discuss the role of Hollywood in "getting the right ideological message across not only to Americans, but also to the Hollywood public around the globe"⁷. As a consequence, Hollywood mainstream cinematic responses have immensely contributed into fashioning movies that capitalize on pro-American sentiment to extol the virtues of the American vision of the world, display American socio-political values and reposition American perceptions of

geo-power on the global stage. It is to this respect that the events of 9/11 are aesthetically and politically mobilized and manipulated in numerous cinematic texts in order to staunch American patriotic values in the face of seemingly undefeatable odds, implying, in the process, the point that securing American national identity is an essential step towards redefining American identity on the global scale.

Indeed, the rhetoric discourse of the "war on terrorism" has provided fertile grounds for Hollywood movie-makers and entertainers to reconfigure the role of the US in world geo-politics. By moulding plots, settings and landscapes to tell geopolitical tales, Hollywood geopolitical movies, in other words, subscribe to American foreign policies, using "war on terrorism" as a starting point for dramatizing American geopolitical anxieties and sensibilities in the Middle East. In so doing, Hollywood popular culture and cinematographic representations of distant geographies and cultures have shifted, or have been made to shift, from producing films preoccupied with Western cultural supremacy to producing films framed by geopolitics and American foreign policies.

Themes of violence, melodrama, heroism and the role of American position in world politics underpin most of post-9/11 cinematic texts. One can consider here, for instance, movies like *Fahrenheit 9/11* (2004), *Rendition* (Gavin Hood, 2007), *Charlie Wilson's War* (2007), *In the Valley of Elah* (2007), *Redacted* (2008), *The Hurt Locker* (2008), and *Zero Dark Thirty* (2012). On their surface, films of this period seem to reiterate the Orientalizing discourse that basically justifies American intervention and involvement in the Middle East. Images of American heroes who epitomize American values and who heroically face and conquer the forces of "evil" in the "exotic" and "dangerous" lands are repeatedly highlighted to display America as the "benevolent" hegemon. Deep down, however, the production and codification of Hollywood cinematic texts after 9/11 are more than simply portraying Middle East through Orientalizing lenses

of danger and exoticism that denigrate and essentialize the lived reality of the region. Indeed, the use of the locations such as Saudi Arabia, Iraq and Afghanistan serves to emphasize the geopolitical importance of the "Other" landscape for American quest for geo-power. Thus, the very specific geographic contexts in which American heroism versus the Other's villainy happens tell more about what America stands for than simply what the Other must discursively represent. As Peter Van Ham states, "the events of 9/11 not only triggered renewed efforts to market 'Brand USA' and US policies, but also generated a process of reflection on what 'America' actually stands for (or, perhaps better, should stand for)"⁸.

In fact, at the heart of Hollywood cinematic texts in contemporary time is the branding of USA nation as a modern empire intent to dominate the world politics. The construction of Middle Eastern spaces as "wild zones" in need of military ethos and American violence can only be understood in the context of how American policy-makers use the apparatus of Hollywood cinema to present America as a unilateral force which alone takes the burden of bringing peace to the world⁹. Read in this context, the Hollywood codifications of American adventures, surveillance technologies and disciplinary power structures inform the way American empire and Hollywood industry harness their efforts to redefine and remap American perceptions of global power. Indeed, the presence of American military power policing and disciplining the Middle East has many of the characteristics of imperial power. Using force and violence to impose order and meaning upon the space, interfering into Middle Eastern states' affairs coupled with America's entire war on terror in the region could all be interpreted as an exercise in imperialism seeking to protect American imperial geo-strategic and military interests in areas beyond its territorial boundaries. George Kieh concurs that the United States' military intervention in the Middle East was not propelled by "the lofty ideals of democracy", but was indeed prompted by "exigencies of imperialism". He puts it clearly that "the [US]

military intervention was ostensibly designed to maintain and expand the United States' politico-security and economic stranglehold on the Middle East"¹⁰.

Accordingly, what intensifies much the drama of the American intervention in the Middle East is the settings in which these dramas are played out. In particular, given its extreme geo-circumstances, the Middle East landscape offers dramatic possibilities for branding American nation-state and dramatizing its geopolitical sensibilities. In other words, the territoriality of Middle East serves as a projection zone for U.S power; a geographical space which enables them to see themselves as a superpower while they displace their own nationalism, geopolitics and violence upon the region. Therefore, rather than reducing American/Middle East conflict to merely cultural and civilizational factors, the delineation of Middle East is in fact geopolitically driven. Gearoid Ó Tuathail notes that "to designate a conflict a civilizational one is to determine its character in a definitive and totalizing manner. It is to impose a closure upon events, situations, and peoples. The geographical specificity and place-based particularity of conflicts are reduced to terms of a civilizational script"¹¹.

This paper is an extension of recent work in "critical geopolitics"¹² on film as a genre that is worth investigation. By drawing on literature from popular geopolitics, geocriticism, visual politics and postmodernism, this study interrogates the ways in which the movie, *The Kingdom* (2007), appropriates and manipulates the discourse of "war on terror" within the broader framework of American foreign-policy and international relations more particularly. The geopolitical codes, the visual geopoliticized rhetoric of screened landscapes and the discursive constructions of otherness, violence, heroism, melodrama and trauma all provide illuminating examples of how these various interdependent registers of mapping and reproducing the Middle East circulate and resonate across the continuum formed by popular culture and world politics in the film under study, *The Kingdom*. To do so, the research is divided into three sections. The first section begins by examining the complex interconnections between

cinema, politics and representation in order to scrutinize how "popular culture", "world politics" and "representation" are complex and contested concepts, as the relations between and among them are complex and dynamic. In so doing, the research reads popular culture not only as an object for analysis, but also as a form of political communication wherein global politics are encoded and disseminated. The other two sections are devoted to the analysis of the geopoliticized narratives related specifically to the ways in which *The Kingdom* narrativizes a variety of anxieties associated with America's current position in world affairs. Moving beyond the artistic merits of landscapes and characterization, the research examines how tropes that inform Orientalist discourse are activated and accommodated in post-9/11 Hollywood cinema to serve specific geopolitical agendas. Power, knowledge, surveillance and disciplining are also examined to investigate the ways in which the film naturalizes its violent approach to Middle East in a broadly inflicted geopolitical narrative.

2. American Popular Orientalism and the Reproduction of "Self"/"Other" Identities: A Geopolitical Dimension

Because "identities are constructed... in relation to what they are not"¹³, producing and reproducing the "Other" which is anti-thesis of the "Self" has been a prerequisite condition to the well-definition and formation of the "Self" for ages. Most often, the relationship between the "Self" and the "Other" is characterized by alterity: the "Other" is what the "Self" is not. Accordingly, the "Other" becomes associated with negative traits, whereas the "Self" implicitly holds positive attributes. This relational sense of identity, however, necessitates demonization, dehumanization, and vilification of the "Other". Furthermore, this dialectic relationship to the "Other" is enmeshed in a relationship of power wherein the dominant "Self" constructs and defines the "Other" in ways that

accord to specific cultural, political and ideologically-laden discourses and interests. In his analysis of asymmetrical power relations between the "Self" and the "Other", the East and the West, Edward Said posits that, "the relationship between Occident and Orient is a relationship of power, domination, of varying degrees of a complex hegemony."¹⁴

Since America, therefore, is a cultural, economic and military superpower, its enduring constructions of the "Other" as "villainous", "threatening" and "violent ideological zealots", while the American "Self" assumes the contrasting virtues, becoming "civilized", "moral" and "humanitarian", promote sharp distinctions between the Middle East and the United States. Because of such asymmetrical power relationships, therefore, the dominant "Self" is able to theorize about and define the "Other". For this sort of binary constructions and anxieties to be culturally and politically validated and legitimized, they need to be disseminated to the audiences in order to be widely accepted as true demarcations between the "Self" and the "Other", between the Oriental "villainy" and the American "heroism", thus justifying America's intervention and involvement in the Middle East.

The movie under study speaks volume to this sense of relationality, ambivalence, power-knowledge asymmetrical relationships, and the desire to project America as an international hegemon. Starring Jamie Foxx as Ronald Fleury, Chris Cooper as Grant Sykes, Jennifer Garner as Janet Mayes, and Jason Bateman as Adam Leavitt, *The Kingdom*, directed by Peter Berg, was released on September 28, 2007 in the genre of drama, politics, and war. The movie's plot centers on a wave of terrorist attacks committed by Abu Hamza, a "fundamentalist" Islamic "terrorist", and his followers against "innocent" American civilians during a softball game at an American oil company housing compound in Ryyad, Saudi Arabia. In response, four American FBI special agents are dispatched to the scene to investigate the terrorist attack and bombing of an American facility by "evil" ideologues. Upon landing on the desert of the

kingdom, the FBI team is met by Colonel Faris al-Ghazi, the commander of the Saudi State Police Force, who advises them of how to act in a hostile environment. Later, they are invited to the palace of Saudi Prince Ahmed bin Khaled for dinner (Mayes is excluded because of her gender, which implies the "backwardness" and "rigidity" ascribed to the East) in order to imply a kind of collaboration between the two states against terrorism. From now on it will be a showdown between the FBI heroes and the villains; the more powerful the villains are, the greater are the heroes. Lead by Ronald Fleury and assisted by Faris al-Ghazi, the FBI team brings down the insurmountably "evil" forces that America must face in order to bring about peace and security to a land that is presented as barbarian and hostile to the progressive ethos and values of the American nation-state. Displaying the confrontation with the "evil" in this way, the moral message of *The Kingdom* conferred to the audience is that anything, and everything that can be done to murder the "villains", must be done, not only to exterminate the threatening "Other", but more importantly to reconfigure the role of American as "the legitimate gendarme of the world."¹⁵

Indeed, the release of *The Kingdom* can be interpreted as indicative of American geopolitical anxieties regarding its military position in the world and the search for a new threat of terrorist attack to justify this anxiety. In other words, the need to create a new Enemy after the fall of the Soviet empire has been a prerequisite need for American policy makers and Hollywood film entertainers in order to rationalize the US extraterritorial military intervention in the Middle East. The explicit terrorist attacks, military invasions and emerging enemies in this film, therefore, demonstrate how far are geopolitical interests and anxieties are manifest in the consciousness of American policy makers, film producers and their audience in the post-9/11 world. To attain its geopolitical goals, as a consequence, the movie's characterization of the "Other" developed into worst manifestations: the constructions of the Arabs/Muslims as the Enemy. This intensified construction which demonstrates the transition from

the "Other" to the Enemy has been, however, a condition for the well-projection of the American "Self", for it has become "more and more difficult to imagine who we are without reference to our enemy [...] Without him who would we blame for the slings and arrows, the failures, the wounds, the inchoate anger, the gnawing frustration, the injustice."¹⁶

The Kingdom begins on battlefield, in a lull in combat operations between the forces of "good" and the "evil". Prior to this, the camera shows American families playing baseball and enjoying barbecue, but constantly cuts to zoom in Abu Hamza from a faraway distance on a top building controlling the terrorist operation that his followers are tasked to destroy lives of dozens of American residents in a nameless city in Saudi Arabia. The bombing operation is successfully implemented; dead corpses of American civilians fill the screen, and then the camera cuts to Abu Hamza murmuring words in Arabic thanking God for the success of his "evil" plans. To further aggravate the feelings of the audience, the camera depicts one of Abu Hamza's followers citing the testimony then blows himself up and tragically kills the rest of survived people around him while pretending to save them. The figure of Abu Hamza then is presented as representative of everything that America stands against. He is the leader of the terrorist group and the representative of God to his followers. He is shot three times indoctrinating "fundamentalist" thinking into the minds of a group of little kids. The scene implies how the terrorist network in the Middle East is in a constant conspiracy to destroy the "ideals" of American culture. Little kids are portrayed in the Muslim costume devoting their attention wholeheartedly to the Abou Hamza's "extremist" discourse, and express their willing to bomb Americans as a response to the "call" of their faith. The shooting of the Saudi Abou Hamza and his faithful group in this way invokes Berg's political ends to personalize Abou Hamza and his 'extremist' preaches to Bin Laden, implying that just like Abou Hamza Bin Laden's "extremism" had started in the same way before "his" attacks of September 11 took place. The prolonged scenes of

the "Other" preparing bombs, intercut with significant scenes depicting mosques, followed by extreme attacks, are not only demeaning depictions of the "Other", but can also be defined as a threat to America's position as a global power.

Furthermore, the enemies encountered in this film are but faces viewed through the close-ups of the camera. They are dehumanized to the point that they are not recognized as people with their own full agency and motivation. They act only in response to fanatical dictations communicated to them by their leader, Abu Hamza. Their crudeness is also manifested in their use of weaponry as the brutality of its effects does not discriminate between its targets, implying that the enemy are backwards, technologically and morally, as their bombs against American civilians are incapable of discerning between friend and foe, innocent and guilty, therefore constructing the "enemy" as entirely uncompromising in the pursuit of their sinister goals. This suggests, however, that although the villains are incompetent and backward, they still appear as powerful and dangerous. This is consistent with the paradoxical view of the Orient, which is inferior to the West, yet "it has always been endowed with greater potential to power (usually destructive) than the West"¹⁷. This is not to say, however, as Edward Said highlights, that the Orient possesses more power than the West but it is because as it is "backward" and "precipitous", the little power it produces becomes threatening and dangerous.

The discursive construction of the "Other" as enemy in this film and others after the appalling events of 9/11, threatens, in fact, the geopolitical and geo-economic stability of the United States in the Middle East and in the international world by extension. Nonetheless, the conflict with the "evil" "Other" is necessary in order to bring about codes of morality, heroism, humanity and nationalism that the film confers to the four American FBI agents who are tasked to redefine American domestic and foreign policies in overseas. As previously noted, post-9/11 Hollywood movies tell more about what defines

American identity than simply how the "Other" must discursively and cinematically be introduced. Nonetheless, the "violent" "Other" is inevitably demanded for this relational meaning to take place. The film introduces FBI agents possessing all the heroic, humanitarian and distinguishing traits that separate them from the forces of "evil". Throughout the most of the film, the camera follows the movements of Ronald Fleury and his team sacrificing their lives to bring peace and stability to Saudi Arabia, and the Middle East by large. The latter, as helpless as it is, could not save itself from the power destruction of its terrorists, which is symptomatic of Orientalist discourse that the Middle East cannot save itself, therefore it needs to be rescued. The heroic American characters are then called upon to save the day. It is, therefore, this construction of Manichean antagonism between "extremist" enemy and American "heroes" that discursively structures the narrative and establishes the grounds for the projection of American nationalist sensibilities and geopolitical anxieties.

By constructing the protection of freedom and democratic values as definitely an American duty, the depiction of FBI heroes in *The Kingdom* as "freedom fighters" draws clear parallels with American military action around the globe. Endowed with all "positive", "humanitarian" and "heroic morals", the FBI agents are portrayed struggling heroically in exotic landscapes "specified as in need of pacification and administration due to the absence of such social attributes in such places not blessed with the benefits of civilization"¹⁸. In the process, FBI agents, displayed as bearers of civilization and order, live out the codes of virtuous warriors who stand in for American honour, values and power. Throughout the film, the camera follows their movements keeping them in center frame as they fight against the forces of evil in order to establish peace in extreme and exotic circumstances. In so doing, they physically reassert American identity, restore its dignity and secure it as the repository virtue against barbaric threats to the values it stands for. Responding with alacrity, therefore, FBI agents determine to exterminate scores of terrorists and

heroically kill Abu Hamza and his followers. United and victorious, Fleury, Mayes, Sykes and Leavitt celebrate their victory and return to America. The victory of American agents and the defeat of the "Other" is essential to the structure of the narrative. Seen from a relational perspective, the defeat of the enemy resolves tensions and divisions within the "Self". The "Self" achieves its beingness and becomes whole again only upon eliminating the "Other". Pierre Biskind posits that in order to understand the ideology upon which films derive their significance, "it is essential to ask who lives happily even after one dies ... and why?"¹⁹. The victorious ending of *The Kingdom* is explicitly associated with the eradication of Arab characters. To this context, the prevalent concept of heroism and villainy as encapsulated by Porteous's statement: "one murder made a villain, millions made a hero"²⁰ speaks volume to the workings of the war narrative in this film.

Indeed, the cinemagraphic portrayals of FBI warriors confronting perils in strange lands for "freedom" and "security" provide the central moral message for the "right" conduct through which their violence can morally be justifiable. In contradistinction to the discursive dehumanization of the "Other" enemy as immoral, violent, and having no sense of restraint, the American heroes retain positive and humanitarian traits; although willing to sacrifice their own life to fight villainy, they certainly will never deliberately sacrifice the life of the innocent. In conferring this sense of moral superiority to FBI agents, the film shows their struggle as "noble" and "humane". In this regard, the moral message of *The Kingdom* conferred to the audience is that American violence ought to be understood nonetheless as noble, whereas the violence depicted against the "enemy" is sanctioned and justified. *The Kingdom* doesn't show Arabs as victims, actually it undermines this idea. *The Kingdom* follows an established tradition in Hollywood films whereon Arabs are presented "only as perpetrators of terror, never as victims."²¹

Moreover, the normative workings of melodrama depicted in *The Kingdom* coupled with sensibilities of American nationalism they serve equally underpin the narrative, shape the American audience's consciousness and reconfirm a sense of national belonging. In fact, *The Kingdom* relies on a number of strategies to mobilize a particular conception of identity, one that triggers feelings of American national harmony and togetherness. First, the plot narrative creates an emotional connection between audience and nation: a sense of safety and contentment with the nation was then juxtaposed with feeling of fear from the "Other". In the process, narratives of national cohesion and togetherness are visualized through the victimization of American civilians in order to mobilize national consciousness in the minds of American audiences. Simultaneously, the campaign theme developed in the narrative serves the aim of reaching unity and harmony through diversity, reflecting and emphasizing therefore the unified perceptions of American identity and nationhood. The diverse representations of FBI characters in terms of race and gender, all sacrificing their lives for the sake of their nation branding, engender a patriotic response to who "we are" and reinforces the narrative of national togetherness. This is indeed reminiscent to George W. Bush's speech to the nation after 9/11, in which he stated that: "these acts of mass murder were intended to frighten our nation into chaos and retreat. But they have failed. Our country is strong [...] A great people has been moved to defend a great nation"²². Following this line of narrative, the film introduces American FBI characters who exhibit staunch patriotic values in their long confrontation with the villains in faraway places. Moreover, they are all driven by a belief in what America represents, and are ready to do whatever necessary to protect their nation. In the process, they show resolve, strength and loyalty towards American national values they stand for. Their ability to achieve victory through adversity, to struggle with a fighting spirit to the end against the violent and ideological zeal of their enemies is

playful in the construction of a national identity that evokes a sense of pride and admiration for Americans.²³

Furthermore, the mobilization of trauma discourse, victimhood and redemption are explicitly advanced in the narrative of *The Kingdom* for the purposes of prioritizing, excusing, and ultimately redeeming the American body. Painful and horrific scenes of brutal actions of terrorists are intensified by the affective strategies the film employs to arouse feelings of patriotism and national unity. The horrific scenes of American dead corpses, the tears of Janet Mayes, and the crashing of the planes into the towers play an important role in triggering emotions of fear, anxiety, and insecurity, which generate a sense of trauma and victimization in the eyes of the audience. In addition, the graphic torture of Adam Leavitt, while fighting against "terrorists", is melodramatically displayed to emphasize the suffering inflicted upon the American male body in order to generate a sense of sympathy for his victimized body. Linda Williams posits that "the basic vernacular of American moving pictures consists of a story that generates sympathy for a hero who is also a victim and that leads to a climax that permits the audience, and usually other characters, to recognize the character's moral value"²⁴. The American body, in other terms, is thoroughly privileged throughout the film. The suffering of FBI agents is visually emphasized to reassert the mythology of the American body as "benevolent", "vulnerable" and "victimized". In other words, melodrama, as a representational device, is deployed repetitively in this film for the sake of augmenting emotional intensification and sensational identification. Thus, to further maintain a sense of the melodramatic, *The Kingdom*, as an action-thriller film, makes use of fundamental conventions of melodrama: moral polarization of "good" versus "evil", "noble" heroic characters, heightened emotion, and sensationalism (emphasis on action and violence), are all effectively deployed to advance the over-dramatic plot-line of the narrative, which is designed to particularly play on the spectators' emotions. Accordingly, by exploiting the

trauma discourse, the film makes a clear-cut difference and distinction between the American body and the Arab/Muslim body. While the pain of the American body is prioritized and exceptionalized, the body of the "Other" is evacuated, dehumanized and denigrated. In a nutshell, the popular rhetoric that manipulated the events of 9/11, upon which the movie draws its plot, is in fact mobilized as a strategy to legitimize the presence of America in the Middle East. In so doing, the narrative assumes a geopolitical form to maintain a sense of American exceptionalism.

3. Geography, Geopolitics and Power Surveillance: Staging the Middle East

"Geopolitics produced international politics as theater: geography was the stage, politics the drama, and geopolitics the detached observation of this representational spectacle."²⁵

The opening sequences of *The Kingdom* with a gripping montage that briefly documents the history of the kingdom of Saudi Arabia since its foundation in 1932 are playful in the construction of a geopolitically narrative that underpins the plot structure of the movie. Indeed, the opening scenes together with the geopolitical, geo-economic, cultural and historical information they convey are carefully chosen and displayed to guide and structure the understanding of the audience towards an acceptance of the difficult circumstances faced by American FBI government agents in their war against the "Other" enemy, thereby justifying America's territorial invasion of the Middle East. As we watch these introductory scenes, a voice-over narrates that Wahabis (Saudi Islamic warriors) are fiercely anti-Western presence in the kingdom and wanted to go back in time to a pure Islam that was not threatened by the West. Saudi Arabia at that time was the number one country that produced oil in the world, whereas America was the number one oil consumer in the world. The voice-over continues to tell that America claimed that the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

needed a security from USA. With the regulation of commercialization, the king of Saudi Arabia accepted it. As a consequence, a partnership was produced between Saudi Arabia and America in 1938, which was named as Arabian American Oil Company (ARAMCO). The voiceover goes on to inform the audience that in 1945 President Roosevelt and Ibnu Saud had a meeting which resulted in signing a unity agreement between East and West, but the Wahhabi movement rejected this unity on the grounds that America supported Israel in the Arab war versus Israel in 1970. Also worth attention in these introductory scenes is the display of the figures of Saddam Hussein and Osama bin Laden. The voice-over recounts that during the Gulf war, bin Laden offered help to the kingdom of Saudi Arabia to destroy Iraq with his Afghan Mujahdidin (warriors) and defeat Saddam Hussein in Kuwait, but Saudi Arabia got a good offer from the United States army. Because of that rejection, Osama bin Laden did not like the cooperation between the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia and the USA. Then, the movie cuts to a plane crashing into a big building to imply that bin Laden's reaction against America was the motif behind the tragedy of 9 September 2011.

This short, but very geopoliticized introductory documentation, is, however, implicitly overloaded with ideologically imbued assemblages of information, geopolitical implications and imperial intents that the film is dedicated to propagandizing the increasingly enfranchised masses into believing American imperial expansionism has been in everyone's interest in Saudi Arabia and the Middle East region as a whole. The emphasis on the Middle East landscape in these documentary sequences, therefore, merits further investigation as it is the battlefield stage upon which world geopolitics are dramatically played out. The visual rhetoric of screened landscape displayed in the movie informs the motivations of the characters, creates the mood, and frames the film's narrative around a valorization of the U.S military involvement in Middle East. In other words, the landscape—in its screened depictions - moulds the place to the needs

of namely geopolitical production. Through specific unnerving camera angles, low lighting, anguish and despair atmosphere, which produce the affect of extreme fear in an enclosed space similar to the regular view of Cold War cinema, the opening of the film presents the Middle East as hostile to human beings; it is a dark and foreboding space, one that borrows from the Orientalist stock images and tropes prevalent in the literary sources outlined by Edward Said in his *Orientalism*. Then, the background screen turns black, and the featured landscape is a deserted, horrific place. The implied purpose is to present a geopoliticized landscape of extreme otherness, thus legitimizing American military interventionism in the region.

Filled with intense violence, *The Kingdom* produces an imaginative geography that seeks to orientate audiences, as well as emotional attachments and enmities that shape what is considered to be politically possible and desirable. Moreover, interruptions of the voice-over with landscape depictions isolate and restrict the gaze of the viewer before they are transported to the battlefield, which is a vast, desolate, and harsh world. Indeed, the film's construction of the locale for the drama is instrumental to its geopolitically influenced narrative. It is through such visual politics of essentializing the "Other" landscape that the movie can provide the moral vocabulary into which narratives of "right" conduct and the American imperial violence could be morally justifiable.

In its discursive mapping of the Middle East, the film relies on a number of established coherent strategies to draw up, spatialize and dominate the Middle East geography. That the Middle East is configured as an ideologically rigid and unchanging place in *The Kingdom* is not, however, perpetuated as being only culturally different, but its geostrategic geography is what counts in the American imperial perpetual struggle over space in global politics. However, still the visualized fetishistic constructions of the Middle East as culturally different and threatening is essential to the film's plot narrative as it seeks to naturalize and legitimize American territorial invasion of the Middle East

region. This brings to mind Samuel Huntington's thesis of "cultural civilization" in which he reduces East-West conflict to merely culture and civilization²⁶. In other words, Huntington's "clash of civilization" rhetoric propagates the idea that the conflict between Western world and the non-Western world are over clashes that are ideological, cultural and religious rather than political and economic, which is indeed the same rhetoric used by the American administration to legitimize its geopolitical efforts to remap the Middle East. Huntington's civilizational discourse, however, is remarkably simplistic and comprehensively flawed as it deliberately overlooks the geographical and geopolitical specificities of conflicts which overwhelmingly structure most of the knowledge produced about the Middle East. Richard Rubenstein and Jarle Crocker, for instance, note that "Huntington has replaced the nation-state, the primary playing piece in the old game of realist politics, with a larger counter: the civilization. But in crucial respects, the game itself goes on as always"²⁷. Corroborating a similar view, Tuathail posits that "Huntington's thesis is not about the clash of civilizations. It is about making global politics a clash of civilizations."²⁸

Informed by geopolitical and geo-economic orientations, *The Kingdom*, as a geopolitically-inclined text, displays geo-graphing politics and geo-power anxieties as central to its dramatic narrative. That is, the imaginative geography propagated in this film together with the desire to produce international politics geographically is specifically driven by political and economic interests. The "imaginative geography"²⁹ elaborated by Edward Said in his *Orientalism* illuminates the manner in which such Western Orientalist imagination shapes the geopolitical and geo-economic discursive mapping of the Middle East. With American Orientalism, more particularly, the imaginative geography of the Middle East landscape is primarily motivated by economic and corporate interests centered mainly on access to oil supply and the domination over the region. Indeed, the Middle East is perceived as "a subsystem of acute strategic

importance to the rest of the world. For local and external powers there are many immutable interests over which to compete and such competition is a major contributory factor to the reputation of the Middle East as the world most volatile and violent region"³⁰. That the opening scenes of the film bring to view the fact that Saudi Arabia has been one of the most rich-oil states in the world and that America was the first oil consumer state in the world is one main imperial motif structuring America's geo-economic struggle over the Middle East. The display of the signed agreement between the two states in this film was meant not only to secure American economic interests in the region, but also to maintain the primacy of the United States over the region, thereby countering the emergence of other external political-economic powers seeking to project their presence in the region, namely China as an emergent threat to U.S primacy in world affairs.

Another constitutive and fundamental element lying bare America's geopolitical sensibilities and anxieties in *The Kingdom* might be the dramatization of the United States' hegemonic and unilateral sense of power, which assigns itself the role of disciplining the "Other" landscape, and subjugating it to the regulatory power structures of its unilateral military action, knowledge and surveillance technology. John Ikenberry observes that "spurred by its war on terrorism, the Bush Administration has advanced new, provocative ideas about the American unilateral and preemptive use of force –and under this go-it-alone if necessary banner"³¹. He adds that "unilateralism seeks to strengthen American power and unashamedly deploy it on behalf of self-defined global ends"³². To this vein, the mention of the Wahhabi Islamic warriors, Iraq, Afghanistan and Israel intercut with images of Saddam Hussein and bin Laden exhibit American unilateral military actions in the Middle East along with specific geopolitical anxieties that the film narrativizes through practices of power, surveillance and disciplining. That is, by narrating how these figures and countries are anti-American democratic values, the movie legitimizes the violent and disciplinary

structures used to root out anti-voices of American presence and its interests in the region. The audience therefore is encouraged to naturalize American military invasion of Iraq, which ultimately resulted in the dethroning of Saddam's regime and his eventual death four years after the release of *The Kingdom*. Saddam and his political regime had to be removed from the Middle East region not because of Iraq's involvement in the Gulf war, nor for the nuclear weapons his country was supposed to possess as the voiceover emphasizes in the movie, but for his threat to the interests of America and the stability of Israel in the region. Simultaneously, the depiction of bin Laden in the film, the "mastermind" behind the September 11, and who was dramatically shot by American army four years later before the release of *The Kingdom*, is brought to the fore to implicitly reaffirm America's role as a key geopolitical player in the Middle East. Given that bin Laden and Saddam's voices are anti-American geopolitical interests, they therefore must be exterminated in order to establish peace and security in the world.

Moreover, power, surveillance and punishment serve specific geopolitical agendas in *The Kingdom*. While on the surface they are deployed in the context of "war on terror", their disciplining effect, however, works to reterritorialize the identity of the United States, rewrite the meaning of geo-power, and secure U.S geopolitics on the global scene, thereby bringing to the fore the complexities of power, knowledge, geography, and geopolitics. In exploring the intricacy of these concepts, Tuathail posits that "geography is about power. Although often assumed to be innocent, the geography of the world is not a product of nature but a product of histories of struggle between competing authorities over the power to organize, occupy, and administer space"³³. Thus, the very identity of the subject position, be they "geographer", "cartographer", or "geopolitician", coupled with the specific techniques by which geographical and geopolitical objects are projected and presented are all effects of power-knowledge relations. Michael Foucault postulates that power and knowledge

directly imply one another: “there is no power relation without the correlative constitution of a field of knowledge, nor any knowledge that does not presuppose and constitute at the same time power relations”³⁴. His insights on power, knowledge and surveillance are indeed instrumental for decoding the power structures involved in the cinematization of space. For him, power, knowledge and surveillance are three entities which support an integrated system, for he argues that the success of disciplinary power, thus the objectification of the individual, is carried out through three inter-related instruments: "hierarchal observation, normalizing judgment and their combination in a procedure that is specific to it, the examination"³⁵. Indeed, as Foucault highlights, discipline "presupposes a mechanism that coerces by means of observation; an apparatus in which the techniques that make it possible to see induce effect of power on whom they are applied clearly visible"³⁶. In other words, "hierarchal surveillance"³⁷, or the technique of making subjects visible or observable, allows extension of knowledge to sustain its hegemonic mechanism. Following this argument, observing and surveilling can be equated with knowing, thus being dominant, and in the context of the film under study the FBI characters are introduced as possessing the power/knowledge mechanisms, something which allows them to surveil and control the "Other".

Indeed, the issue of surveillance, power and cinema has been important to media scholars. Drawing on Sebastian Lefait's study on the mutual implication of cinema and surveillance, Xiaoning Lu writes that in his study of contemporary film and television programs "[Lefait] suggests that cinema engages surveillance structurally through its fictional creation of surveillance microcosms. In the meantime, by being a reality-capturing device, the cinematic apparatus "translates the problem of the ambiguity of the visible into terms of mediated watching", which is also a matter at the heart of surveillance"³⁸. In a similar vein, Catherine Zimmer concurs that "'surveillance cinema" is not simply the recurring tropes or iconographies of surveillance [...] Rather [...]

"the multiple mediations that occur through the cinematic narration of surveillance, through which practices of surveillance become representational and representational practices become surveillant"³⁹. The Kingdom's violent, disciplinary and surveillance narrative embodies and displays all such practices of power and surveillance exerted upon the Middle East geography. In its screened geopoliticized landscape, the film involves, exhibits, and relies on specific disciplinary and surveillance techniques to counter the Other's severe "threat" to American's national security and geopolitical interests in the region. The opening sequences of the film with aerial top-down views, the evocative display of geopolitically charged panoramas of the landscape, the use of satellite technologies, and the reliance on the FBI's expertise and knowledge to track the Other enemy, all promoted by surveillance technologies, indicate how the movie is structured around power and hierarchized surveillance. As a consequence, through the literal and figurative lens of surveillance, the "Other" becomes objectified, surveilled, recorded and controlled. It is equally through these mechanisms of surveillance that a "scientific", "neutral", "objective", and specialized language (knowledge/truth) about the "Other" is produced and sustained. The film depicts the FBI agents as intelligence experts using satellite reconnaissance technology to navigate and investigate the Middle East. In fact, the camera centers much on the battle against the "Other" enemy in order to emphasize the expertise of the FBI investigators mapping out the movements of terrorists, which ultimately leads to the murder of Abou Hamza. Hence, by engaging surveillance mechanisms in its cinematic narrative, the film attributes the tropes of scientific authority, neutrality to FBI agents, thereby justifying their military intervention in the Middle East. The consistency with which this expertise and power are imagined point to the rationalization and disciplining qualities of American imperialism regarding its intervention and involvement in the Middle East. In other words, surveillance, as a mode of power, has been crucial to the United States' geopolitical discourse and its military presence in

the Middle East. The landscape of Saudi Arabia depicted in this film as a geostrategic location is in fact an extension of American military base on the real grounds. The actual presence of American military camp in the region unfolds the American real practices of surveillance, disciplining and punishing the Middle East. In a nutshell, surveilling, disciplining and punishing the Middle East either in fiction or in reality serve the very geopolitical sensibilities of the United States in the region embodied in its global hegemony and imperial expansionism. The link between the aforementioned modalities of power and their effect on the imaginative geography can also be clearly found in the links postulated by Edward Said between imperialism and geography, for he states that imperialism is after all “an act of geographical violence through which virtually every space in the world is explored, charted, and finally brought under control”⁴⁰.

4. Conclusion

Attempting to interrogate the intersections of geopolitics, power, global hegemony and politics of signification manifest in post-9/11 Hollywood cinema, the conclusions reached herein have revealed the ways in which *The Kingdom*, as a geopolitical film, has mediated, reproduced and geopoliticized the Middle East landscape and culture along with the ethos of American militarism, geo-policy-making and economic pursuits in the region. While the research demonstrates how the movie has borrowed from Orientalist stock images and strategies that have long been used to signify the Middle East, it emphasized that 9/11 has manipulated and altered these strategies in substantive ways. In the process, it has demonstrated that the construction and the designation of the spaces of “Middle East” as “wild zones” in need of American intervention was mobilized as an argument for American geopolitical interests and interventionism in the region. Likewise, the analysis has illustrated the

ways in which the film deployed the rhetoric of "war on terrorism" as a narrative strategy to display American geopolitical anxieties, America's fear of losing its way in the world, and its geopolitical efforts to recuperate American perception of geo-power. It has maintained that the discursive constructions of the "Other" as enemy and the delineation of the "Other" landscape as dangerous and volatile in post-9/11 Hollywood cinematic texts are enframed within geopolitics, petro-politics and the desire to project America as a world hegemon intending to dominate international politics. More precisely, the construction of the "Other" as enemy threatening American political and economic interests in the region provided the background against which new forms of geo-power and geopolitical narratives are reinstated and situated. In other words, with the demise of the Cold War and the subsequent collapse of the Soviet Union as the "evil empire", the search for a new threat of terrorist attack, a new geo-political justification for American hegemonic identity and world position, was a prerequisite condition for the reproduction of American hegemony on the global stage. In addition, the study has examined the manner in which such geopolitical sensibilities are mobilized through narratives of melodrama, trauma, victimization, and the burden that American "benevolent" characters must bear to bring peace to the world, therefore emphasizing American exceptionalism and supporting American global hegemony as legitimate. It has interrogated how the film's accommodation and manipulation of history through a brief historical documentary of archival footage of the Middle East is deployed and filtered through the events of 9/11 in order to rewrite and rescue the long and contested history of American foreign policy, economic investment and involvement in the Middle East. In so doing, it shows how the movie's plotline narrative authorizes and validates American knowledge and expertise about the Middle East, which, in other words, might explain American policies of surveillance, discipline and punishment. Ultimately, what is at stake here is a

geopolitical struggle over the space and the desire to reconfigure the role of America as a world hegemony.

Endnotes

[1] Quoted in Andrew Crampton and Marcus Power (2007). *Cinema and Popular Geo-Politics*. London: Routledge. p.4.

[2] For further discussion, see Floribert Patrick C Endong. (2018). "Cinema Globalization and Nation Branding: An Exploration of the Impact of the Nollywood of the Nigerian Image Crisis". *Journal of Globalization Studies*, Volume 9, Issue 1.

[3] Quoted in Klaus Dodds (2008). "Hollywood the Popular Geopolitics of the War on Terror", *Third World Quarterly*, Vol.29: 8. 1621-1637.

[4] Quoted in Jiong, Zhang (2017). *Literature and Literary Theory in Contemporary China*. Trans. Yang Limeng and Wu Yischeng. London and New York: Routledge, p.109.

[5] Jutta Weldes and Christina Rowely (2015). "So, How Does Popular Culture Relates to World Politics?" In Federica Caso And Caitlin Hamilton (Eds.). *Popular Culture and World Politics: Theories, Methods, Pedagogies*. Bristol: E-International Relations Publishing, p.19.

[6] Andrew Crampton and Marcus Power, *Cinema and Popular Geo-Politics*, p.1.

[7] Ibid.

[8] Peter Van Ham (2008). "War, Lies, and Videotape: Public Diplomacy and USA's War on Terrorism." *Sage Publications*, Volume34, Issue 4, p.434.

[9] See Thomas J. Cobb (2020). *American Cinema and Cultural Diplomacy: The Fragmented Kaleidoscope*.UK: Palgrave Macmillan.

[10] Georeg Klay Kieh (1992). "Western Imperialism in the Middle East: The Case of the United States' Military Intervention in the Persian Gulf". *Arab Studies Quarterly*, Volume 14, Issue 1, p.1.

[11] Gearoid Ó Tuathail (1996). *Critical Geopolitics: The Politics of Writing Global Space*. London: Routledge, p.192.

[12] According to Gearoid Ó Tuathail, "Critical geopolitics is distinguished by its problematization of the logocentric infrastructures that make "geopolitics" or any spatialization of the global political scene possible. It problematizes the "is" of "geography" and "geopolitics," their status as self-evident, natural, foundational, and eminently knowable realities ... Rather

than innocent sites of declarative facts and constative statements about the world, these signs ["geography" and "geopolitics"] mark the site of space/power/knowledge production systems, operations that script the actors, settings, and dramas of global politics in deeply geo-politicized ways." (Ó Tuathail, Gearoid, *Critical Geopolitics: The Politics of Writing Global Space*, p.52.)

- [13] Katherin Woodward (1997), (Ed). *Identity and Difference*. London: Sage Publications, p.35.
- [14] Edward Said (1978). *Orientalism*. London and Henley: Routledge and Kegan Paul, p.5.
- [15] Floribert Patrick C. Endong (2018). "Cinema Globalization and Nation Branding: An Exploration of the Impact of the Nollywood of the Nigerian Image Crisis", *Journal of Globalization Studies*, Volume 9, Issue 1, p.79.
- [16] Hirshberg S. Mathew (1993). *Perpetuating Patriotic Perceptions: The Cognitive Function of the Cold War*. New York: Praeger, p.47.
- [17] Edward Said (1981). *Covering Islam: How Media and Experts Determine How See the Rest of the World*. New York: Pantheon Books, p.4.
- [18] Simon Dalby (2013). "Challenging Cartographies of Enmity: Empire, War and Culture in Contemporary Militarization". In Anna Stavrianakis and Jan Selby (Eds.), *Militarism and International Relations: Political Economy, Security, Theory*. London and New York: Routledge, p.38.
- [19] Salen Alaswad (2000). "Hollywood Shoots the Arab: The Construction of the Arab in American Culture". Diss. The Temple University Graduate Board.
- [20] Ibid.
- [21] Jack Shaheen (1990). "Screen Images of Palestinians in 1980s". In Paul Loukides and Linda K. Fuller (Eds.), *Beyond the Stars: Stock characters in American popular film, Volume 1*. Bowling Green Ohio: Bowling Green State University Popular Press, p.57.
- [22] De Richard Jackson (2005). *Writing the War on Terrorism: Language, Politics and Counter-terrorism*. Manchester and New York: Manchester University Press, p.191.
- [23] Jake Pembroke (2015). "Constructing American Identity and the Terrorist 'Other': Representations of Foreign Policy and Identity in post-2007 Hollywood Cinema". *Dissertation. The New Birmingham Review*. Vol. 1. No. 1. pp.177-225.
- [24] Nestingen, Andrew. (2008). *Cinema and Fantasy in Scandinavia: Fiction, Film, and Social Change*. Copenhagen: Museum Tusulanum Press, p.115.
- [25] Gearoid Ó Tuathail, *Critical Geopolitics: The Politics of Writing Global Space*, p.178.
- [26] In his article, *The Clash of Civilizations?*, published in *Foreign Affairs* in Summer 1993 (later expanded in his book (1996) *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of World Order*), Samuel Huntington posits that "it is my hypothesis that the fundamental source of conflict in this new world will not be primarily ideological or primarily economic. The great divisions among humankind and the dominating source of conflict will be cultural. Nation States will remain the

most powerful actors in world affairs but the principal conflicts of global politics will occur between nations and groups of different civilizations. The clash of civilizations will dominate global politics. The fault lines between civilizations will be battle lines of the future" (Samuel Huntington P, (Summer 1993) "The Clash of Civilizations?" *Foreign Affairs* Vol. 72, No. 3, p.22.

[27] Richard Rubenstein and Jarle Crocker (Fall 1994), "Challenging Huntington." *Foreign Policy*. No. 96. As cited in Gearoid Ó Tuathail, *Critical Geopolitics: The Politics of Writing Global Space*, p. 194.

[28] Gearoid Ó Tuathail, *Critical Geopolitics: The Politics of Writing Global Space*, p.195.

[29] In his discussion of how "imaginative geography" functions in Orientalist discourse, Edward Said writes that "It [Orientalism] is rather a distribution of geopolitical awareness into aesthetic, scholarly, economic, sociological, historical, and philological texts; it is an elaboration not only of a basic geographical distinction but also of a whole series of "interests" (Edward Said. *Orientalism*, p.12).

[30] James Wyllie (2005). "The Middle East: Arena of Competition and Conflict". In Trevor C. Salmon (Ed.), *Issues in International Relations*. New York: Routledge, p.189.

[31] Ikenberry G. John (2003). "Is American Multilateralism in Decline". *Perspectives On Politics*, Volume 1, Issue 3, p.533.

[32] Ibid.

[33] Gearoid Ó Tuathail, *Critical Geopolitics: The Politics of Writing Global Space*, p.1.

[34] Michael Foucault (1995). *Discipline and Punishment: The Birth of the Prison*. Trans. Alan Sheridan. New York: Vintage Books, p.33.

[35] Ibid., p.170.

[36] Ibid., pp.170-171.

[37] For an in-depth study, see Foucault's analysis of "Hierarchal surveillance", "normalizing judgment", and the "examination", as three fundamental processes involved in discipline. Michael Foucault, *Discipline and Punishment: The Birth of the Prison*, pp.170-76, 177-83, 184.

[38] Xiaoning Lu (2017). "The Might of the People: Counter-Espionage Films and Participatory Surveillance in the Early PRC". In Karen Fang (Ed.), *Surveillance in Asian Cinema: Under Eastern Eyes*. New York and London: Routledge, p.13.

[39] Catherine Zimmer (2015). *Surveillance Cinema*. New York and London: New York University Press, p.2.

[40] Edward Said (1993). *Culture and Imperialism*. New York: Vintage Books, p.271.

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